

NOTES

Copper(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with Di(1-phenyltetrazoline)-5,5'-disulphide

B. SINGH*, KAPILESHWAR CHAUDHARY

and

UDAY BHANU

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 30 July 1985, revised 20 June 1986,
accepted 2 August 1986

ORGANIC disulphides are of great biological significance¹⁻³. The complexing behaviour of the heterocyclic disulphide, viz. di(1-phenyltetrazoline)-5,5'-disulphide (DPTDS) with Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been reported elsewhere⁴.

The present paper describes the preparation and structural investigation of the complexes of this ligand with Hg^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Experimental

Di(1-phenyltetrazoline)-5,5'-disulphide was prepared by oxidising 1-phenyltetrazoline-5-thiol (0.2

mol) in ethanolic medium with an ethanolic solution of iodine (0.1 mol). All other chemicals used were of chemically pure grade.

Preparation of complexes: The corresponding metal salt (0.02 mol) was dissolved in aqueous ethanol (50 ml) and the resulting solution was mixed with a solution of the ligand (0.02 mol) in benzene (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 h. Crystals of the complexes separated out on cooling the resulting solution. The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and benzene and dried at 110°. The complexes [Hg(DPTDS)₂Ac₂], [Hg₂(DPTDS)₄X₄] and [Cu(DPTDS)(H₂O)(SO₄)] were obtained in this way (where X=Cl, Br and I). The complex, [Cu(DPTDS)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₂ and [Cu(DPTDS)₂Ac₂].2H₂O separated out on mixing an ethanolic solution of the corresponding salt of Cu^{II} (0.02 mol in 50 ml of ethanol) with a solution of the ligand in benzene (25 ml) and collected as before.

Analytical data of the ligand and complexes are given in Table 1. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in CsI-pellets in the range of 4 000–200 cm⁻¹ with a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the ligand and the Cu^{II} complexes were recorded in nujol with a Carry 14 spectrophotometer. Molar conductivity of the Hg^{II} complexes was measured in DMF by means of a Systronic digital conductometer. Cu^{II} complexes were only partially soluble in DMF and other organic solvents and hence their molar conductivity could not be measured.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Molar conductance in DMF Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} at 28° B.M.
		M	N	S	X		
DPTDS	White	—	31.4 (31.63)	18.41 (18.01)	—	—	—
[Hg ₂ (DPTDS) ₄ Cl ₄]	White	20.53 (20.47)	22.8 (22.87)	13.12 (13.07)	7.2 (7.25)	5.0	—
[Hg ₂ (DPTDS) ₄ Br ₄]	White	18.78 (18.78)	20.91 (20.92)	11.88 (11.99)	14.95 (14.96)	8.0	—
[Hg ₂ (DPTDS) ₄ I ₄]	Light pink	17.24 (17.26)	19.20 (19.27)	11.10 (11.01)	21.84 (21.83)	12.0	—
[Hg(DPTDS) ₂ Ac ₂]	White	10.41 (10.47)	21.84 (21.82)	12.4 (12.47)	—	—	—
[Cu(DPTDS) ₂ Ac ₂].2H ₂ O	Light blue	6.91 (6.81)	24.22 (24.20)	13.81 (13.83)	—	—	1.98
[Cu(DPTDS)(H ₂ O) ₂ (SO ₄)]	Blue	11.58 (11.56)	20.41 (20.38)	17.48 (17.49)	—	—	2.01
[Cu(DPTDS) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Dirty green	7.24 (7.23)	25.6 (25.55)	14.58 (14.57)	8.12 (8.12)	—	2.0

NOTES

TABLE 2—MAJOR INFRARED BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=S}$	ν_{C-S}	ν_{S-S}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-X}	ν_{M-S}
DPTDS	1 290s 1 005sh	1 020m 1 005sh	775s 770vs	525w 500m	—	—	—	—
[Hg ₂ (DPTDS) ₄ Cl ₄]	1 240mb 1 232sh	1 020w 990sh	765vs 760sh	490m	568m 355m	—	355m	300sh
[Hg ₂ (DPTDS) ₄ Br ₄]	1 240w 1 225w	1 015w 990sh	766w 758m 710m	490w	568m 340m	—	—	280w
[Hg ₂ (DPTDS) ₄ I ₄]	1 235sh 1 222m	1 010mb 982m	762s 752m 710w	490w	568m 353m	—	—	280w
[Hg(DPTDS) ₂ Ac ₂]	1 235m	1 020m 998vw	770vs 722w	490w	568m 358m	405w	—	290w
[Cu(DPTDS) ₂ Ac ₂].2H ₂ O	1 235m	1 020m 998vw	750s 680vs	500w	—	380w 360w	—	335m 330m
[Cu(DPTDS)(H ₂ O) ₂ (SO ₄)]	1 230m	1 020m 1 001w	750s 690m	510w	—	385w 380w 360w	—	340m 325m
[Cu(DPTDS) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	1 235w	1 020w 1 008w	750s 700w	510w	—	390w 380w	—	340mb 330mb

s=Strong, vs=very strong, m=medium, mb=medium and broad, w=weak, sh=shoulder.

Results and Discussion

With the exception of [Cu(DPTDS)(H₂O)₂SO₄], which is 1 : 1 complex, all the other complexes are of 1 : 2 type (Table 1). Hg^{II} complexes are highly soluble in DMF and partially soluble in most of the organic solvents. However, cryoscopic determination of the molecular weights of the complexes indicated the monomeric nature of [Hg(DPTDS)₂Ac₂], while the remaining Hg^{II} complexes were dimeric. The iodo-complex, [Hg₂(DPTDS)₄I₄] exhibited abnormal molecular weight. Low conductance (Table 1) of the Hg^{II} complexes in DMF solution corresponded to their non-ionic nature and this justified the formulations [Hg(DPTDS)₂Ac₂] and [Hg₂(DPTDS)₄X₄], where X=Cl, Br and I.

The Cu^{II} complexes, Cu(DPTDS)₂X₂.2H₂O (where, X=Cl, Ac and $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄) were only partially soluble in most of the organic solvents. The room temperature μ_{eff} value of the Cu^{II} complexes were found to be ~2.0 B.M., which corresponded to monomeric Cu^{II} complexes indicating the absence of any Cu—Cu bond in them. The percentage loss of water in the complex [Cu(DPTDS)₂Ac₂].2H₂O at 120° was found to be 3.5 which accounted for its two molecules of water of crystallisation. No such loss of water was found in case of the other two Cu^{II} complexes which indicated the coordinated nature of water molecules in them.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes are given in Table 2. The spectra of Cu^{II} complexes contain broad bands in the regions 3 460–3 440 and 1 630–1 600 cm⁻¹ which may be due to coordinated or lattice water in the complexes. The pattern of metal–ligand bonding in the complexes are revealed from the mode of shifting of ν_{C-S} , $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{S-S} bands of the ligand on coordination. There are two strong bands in the spectrum of the ligand at 775 and 770 cm⁻¹, which have contribution from C—S stretching

vibration⁵ and out-of-plane bending vibration of C—H. In all the complexes, one of these two bands red-shifted to 680–720 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination through sulphur. Bonding through sulphur is also indicated by the red-shifting of S—S stretching band⁶ of the ligand from 525 to 510–490 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Strong bands at 1 595–1 590 and 1 430–1 400 cm⁻¹ in the Hg^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with DPTDS and acetato group indicated that the latter is coordinated as a monodentate ligand⁷. The bands at 1 360(s), 1 190(b, s), 1 112(m) and 600(m, b) cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of [Cu(DPTDS)(H₂O)₂(SO₄)] indicated the bidentate nature of the sulphato group⁸ in this complex.

In the far-infrared spectra of the complexes, the ν_{Hg-S} , ν_{Hg-N} and ν_{Hg-O} (acetate) bands were identified at 280–300, 340–358 and 405 cm⁻¹, respectively. The band at 355 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of [Hg₂(DPTDS)₄Cl₄] arise probably due to Hg—Cl (terminal) stretching mode. Absence of any medium to strong band at 200–300 cm⁻¹ indicated the absence of any Hg—Cl—Hg moiety in this complex. Hg—Br and Hg—I stretching bands normally fall below 200 cm⁻¹, hence could not be identified. The ν_{Cu-O} and ν_{Cu-S} bands in the Cu^{II} complexes were identified at 360–390 and 325–340 cm⁻¹, respectively. Presence of Hg—N in addition to Hg—S bonding is also supported by the presence of a new medium band at 568 cm⁻¹ in all the Hg^{II} complexes, which has definitely some contribution from Hg—N stretching vibration^{9,10}.

Thus it may be concluded that DPTDS acts as (N,S)-bidentate ligand to Hg^{II} and (S,S)-bidentate ligand to Cu^{II} in the complexes.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes exhibited three bands at 975–985, 775–785 and 610–655 nm in the visible region, commonly observed for distorted octahedral Cu^{II}

complexes. Thus the Cu^{II} complexes have most probably distorted octahedral structure.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. N. K. Jha, I.I.T., New Delhi, for the electronic spectra, and to the authorities of Patna University for providing facilities.

References

1. E. D. BERGMANN and D. LAVIO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4948.
2. C. R. MOLLER and V. BLAISE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3858.
3. K. C. JOSHI and A. B. SEN, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1952, **11**, 526.
4. B. SINGH, K. CHAUDHARY and U. BHANU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
5. I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1962, **35**, 1286, 1449, 1456.
6. C. P. BILLOT, A. PERRIN and J. PRIGENT, *Chem. Commun.*, 1970, 676.
7. S. D. ROBINSON and M. F. UTTLEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 1912.
8. R. ESKENAZI, J. BASKOVAN and R. LEVITUS, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 521.
9. L. SACCONI and A. SABATINI, *Nature (London)*, 1960, **186**, 549.
10. K. BRODERSEN, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1957, **290**, 24.

Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes with Tridentate Schiff Base Vanillideneanthranilic Acid

GEETHA PARAMESWARAN* and JESSY CHACKO

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Malappuram-673 695

Manuscript received 9 February 1983, revised 25 June 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

CCOORDINATION ability of different Schiff bases derived from anthranilic acid and their analytical applications have been studied extensively¹⁻⁵. However, Schiff bases derived from vanillin and

amino acids have not been fully investigated. In continuation of our earlier work^{6,7} on vanillideneanthranilic acid complexes of transition metal ions, we report here the results of magnetic and infrared spectroscopic investigations of some new Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes of the above ligand.

Experimental

The ligand vanillideneanthranilic acid (C₁₅H₁₃NO₄; hereafter H₃L) was prepared⁶ by condensing an ethanolic solution of vanillin (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) and anthranilic acid (1.36 g, 0.01 mol), m.p. 174° (Found: C, 66.42; H, 4.80; N, 5.08. C₁₅H₁₃NO₄ calcd. for: C, 66.40; H, 4.83; N, 5.17%).

All metal chlorides used were of A.R. grade.

Isolation of metal chelates: Metal chloride (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml) were refluxed together on a water-bath for 2 h. Metal chelates which separated on cooling were filtered, washed with methanol and finally dried in vacuum. The results of analytical data⁸ are recorded in Table 1.

Physical measurements: The molar conductance of the complexes were measured in nitrobenzene and/or methanol. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. Molecular weights were determined by a Gallenkamp semimicro ebulliometer using dioxan as the solvent. The ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes in nujol were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer and Fourier far-ir spectra were recorded in a Polytec FIR 30 spectrometer. Thermograms were taken using a Stanton TR-1 recording thermobalance.

Results and Discussion

Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} form 1:1 complexes with vanillideneanthranilic acid. Elemental analysis data of these complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are stable against light and atmosphere. The complexes exhibit molar conductance in the range 0.01–7.3 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and are non-electrolytes. The magnetic moments of the com-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND THERMAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Mol. wt Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Λ _M Ω ⁻¹ cm ²	μ _{eff} B.M.	% Loss Found/ (Calcd.)	Decomp. Temp. (peak) K
			Metal	N				
[CoL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Pale pink	546.5 (696.4)	16.16 (16.88)	4.05 (4.04)	7.31	4.73	80 (76.85)	643
[NiL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Pale green	589.4 (694.7)	17.00 (16.98)	4.03 (4.05)	7.31	3.88	80 (78.40)	673
[CuL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Green	555.8 (705.6)	18.00 (18.12)	3.70 (3.99)	0.01	1.84	74 (77.92)	543
[ZnL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Silvery white	560.5 (709.2)	18.97 (18.54)	4.02 (3.97)	1.45	Dis	78 (76.91)	623

* LH₃ = C₁₅H₁₃NO₄.